

Readability Measures for Multiple-Choice and Innovative Items

Abstract

Evaluating readability is important when determining the dimensionality of an assessment, especially when one dimension has disproportionately lengthy stimuli (e.g., charts, tables, narratives, etc.). The current study explores multiple methods for determining the contributions (and lack thereof) of readability in detecting an artificial dimension in innovative items.

Purposes and Perspectives

In order to minimize construct-irrelevant variance, reading demands of an assessment should be “kept to the minimum necessary for the valid assessment of the intended construct” (AERA/APA/NCME, 2014). Therefore, an essential validity check before deploying an exam is to evaluate item readability. Readability is the degree to which a reader can understand text. All items require some degree of reading ability, but reading difficulty should not impede in measuring the main construct of interest. Accreditation exams should have readability levels commensurate to standard textbooks in the same domain; when readability levels surpass standard textbooks, reading ability becomes a prerequisite for answering items correctly. Ensuring that exams have suitable readability levels is crucial to educational equity, especially for populations that have a high percentage of ESL test takers.

However, currently used readability measures are outdated and unreliable. The most commonly used measures pre-date modern computers, such as the Flesch–Kincaid test (1975), the Gunning fog index (1952), the SMOG grade (1969), and Fry graphs (1968). Because computational resources were limited, the formulas to calculate these measures are fairly simple, consisting of word count, syllable count, and sentence count (Kincaid, Fishburne, Rogers, & Chissom, 1975). These formulas were also not intended to be generalizable across age and cultures (Bertam, Rubin, and Starr, 1981) and have been shown to be unreliable classifiers of reading text level (Crossley, Allen, & McNamara, 2011).

Moreover, these readability statistics are not well-suited to evaluating selected-response items. Measures of lexical text diversity, such as the MTLT, voc-D, and HD-D, are not reliable for passages less than 100 words (Koizumi, 2012). Formulas such as the Homan-Hewitt (1994) use vocabulary as part of the calculation, which is inappropriate for licensure exams that use specialized terminology.

Many readability measures are calculated using total number of sentences, whereas multiple-choice items often have sentences spread across an item’s stem and distractors. Unless the items are edited post-hoc, the sentence length measure will be inflated, which skews the readability measures. Editing items post-hoc is not only time-consuming but unreliable. Answer choices that are abbreviated into sentences despite being incomplete sentences result in artificially low readability statistics. Answer choices that are revised to be complete sentences also skew readability statistics and lowers overall lexical diversity. Badgett and Corkill (2010) have proposed a readability measure for examinations, but the method requires manually correcting incomplete sentences. This is a tedious process to complete for hundreds of items and may not reflect the actual reading process.

Methods and data sources

The text of 40 multiple-choice items and 40 innovative items administered as a field test on a large-scale accreditation exam were analyzed separately. Statistics calculated include word

count, character count, syllable count, sentence count, total words per sentence, total syllables per word, number and percent of different words, number and percent of technical words, number of clauses, as well as six commonly used readability measures (Flesch Kincaid, FOG, SMOG, ARI, MTLT, Lexile). Average time taken and item difficulty for each item was also investigated.

A preliminary correlational analysis was separately conducted on the two classes of items to investigate the relationship between the text statistics and an item's loading factor on two-dimensions, with the multiple-choice items loading on one dimension and the innovative items loading on a secondary dimension. Item difficulty was weakly correlated to any of the count statistics and readability measures, however time was strongly positively correlated to several of the text statistics, such as word count, character count, clause count, and syllable count. These measures will be regressed on loading factors to establish whether readability determines the strength of association to a particular factor. This method could be of interest to the test development community looking for better means to investigate test readability, for both selected-response items and more text-heavy items designed to measure higher-order thinking skills.

References

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